

Frameworks For Political Analysis Of The Issue Of Demonstrations In The News Bulletins Of Iraqi Satellite Channels An Analytical Study

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 29, 2021

Accepted:
July 27, 2021

Keywords :

Political Analysis, The Demonstrations, The Government's Policy

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5140295

Abstract

This research deals with the frameworks of political analysis of the issue of the demonstrations in the news bulletins of the Iraqi satellite channels represented by Al-Iraqiya, Dijla and Al-Atija channels, which were selected according to an exploratory study conducted by him. Iraqi Ministry of Foreign Affairs. The researcher concluded to a sample of the public that these channels are the most followed, and the orientations of these three channels differ, where Al-Iraqiya TV represents the official view of the state, while Dijla TV represents a partisan viewpoint opposing the government's policy. While the channel represents the Islamic line and then one of the channels of the Union of Islamic Radios and Channels in Iraq, the research problem was represented in the main question "What are the frameworks for political analysis of the issue of demonstrations in Iraq. Iraqi satellite news releases? This research is descriptive research, and the researcher used the survey method and the content analysis tool, where he analyzed the eight pm news bulletins for the chosen period and mentioned in the time domain of the research, so the analysis was done in a comprehensive inventory method: (an interview represented by (55) interviews on the trend channel, and (50) interviews on Al-Iraqiya channel, and (40) interviews. Interviews on Dijla channel, the researcher reached a number of results, the most important of which are: 1. The frameworks for the proposed solutions to the issue of the demonstrations came first within the frameworks mentioned in the political analysis, due to the interest of political analysts in resolving the issue before it is too late and the situation recedes. Al-Iraqiya channel topped this framework and tried to find solutions and avoid a collision between the government and the demonstrators and sought calm.2. The warning framework came in second place among the frameworks, and the warning frameworks launched by political analysts varied, including warnings to the government in dealing with the demonstrations and not suppressing them, as presented by the Dijla satellite channel, and from there to the demonstrators. Themselves. . Fear of calm exit, according to what was reported by Al-Ittijah and Al-Iraqiya channel. 3.Dijla channel topped the conflict frameworks that were presented with a political analysis and focused on the Iranian-American conflict inside Iraq and the conflict between the demonstrators and the government, and since the first day of the political demonstrations, Dijla channel adopted its support. To the demonstrators and win the audience in all ways. 4. The political analysis focused on the keywords, and the designations differed from one channel to another. Political analysts in Dijla TV stressed the designation of "militias" and pointed out that there are entities affiliated with Iran that are killing protesters. As for the political analysis in the direction, it confirmed the Joker gangs, which accuse them of working for the United States.5. Political analysts highlighted the active forces with different roles, between negative and positive. Dijla channel described Iran's role as an active force with a negative role and a channel that describes the United States as a subversive role in Iraq. As for the religious authority in Najaf as an active force, everyone agreed. Political analysts talk about the paternalistic role it plays in solving the country's problems.

Introduction

With the great development witnessed by the work of satellite channels, especially in the news field, and with the increase in facts and events in the social and political environment, the importance of political analysis in

news bulletins increased, as it provides information that contributes to dismantling, explaining and re-installing issues in ways through which visions and ideas can be reached. It is a forward-looking car that enables the public to understand what is going on around it in the environment in which it lives, and of course political analysis varies according to the politics of the channels and the nature of the political analyst in classifying the event and placing it according to certain frameworks, and the researcher seeks in his research to find a link between political analysis in news releases and the theory of frameworks. The news, which is an attempt to reveal an appropriate theory for application in the media environment, and the role that political analysts play in formulating political issues by placing them in certain frameworks, whether they are reasons, responsibility, ongoing conflicts, or frameworks for solutions that they propose for the solution and other frameworks in which they are formulated. Events are presented to the public.

Methodological framework

First search problem

The research problem revolves around the frameworks of political analysis of the issue of demonstrations in the news bulletins of the Iraqi satellite channels represented by "Al-Iraqiya, Dijla and Al-Mawqif" channel, because of the importance of these channels for the Iraqis. The public and the problem of this research revolve around the following main question: What are the frameworks for political analysis of the issue of demonstrations in news bulletins. Sample of Iraqi satellite channels research?

A number of questions arise from this question, as follows

1. What are the frameworks of political analysis of the issue of the demonstrations that were mentioned in the news bulletins of the Iraqi satellite channels, the sample of the research?
2. What are the keywords mentioned in the political analysis of the topic of the demonstrations in the news releases of the research sample channels?
3. What are the active forces that focused on the political analysis of the demonstrations on satellite channels?

Second, the importance of research

The importance of this research is of two types:

- A. Knowing the importance: This research is the first of its kind that deals with political analysis in the news bulletins of the Iraqi satellite channel. Scientific heritage. .
- B. Importance to society: This importance stems from the importance of political analysis and the information it provides to help the public understand current events, as research helps in accessing public perceptions about art and political methods. The analysis that appears on satellite channels, which is used to identify the gaps in the aspects of work.

Third: Research objectives

The research seeks to achieve the following objectives

- A. Getting to know the frameworks of political analysis of the issue of demonstrations in the news bulletins of the Iraqi satellite channels, the research sample.
- B. Investigating the keywords mentioned in the political analysis of the demonstrations topic in the news releases of the research sample channels.
- C. To reveal the active forces that focus on the political analysis of the issue of the demonstrations in the channels of the research sample.

Fourth: Research method and type

This research is a descriptive research that provides information and explanation for the phenomena to be studied. The survey methodology and the content analysis tool were used on a sample of publications that were subjected to the study in order to know the frameworks of political analysis, and how political analysts framed the issue of demonstrations, to come up with results that lead to a systematic comparison between the three channels.

Fifthly: Research areas

- A. Time range: It was set from (October 1, 2019) to (December 31, 2019)
- B. Subject area: News releases in Iraqi satellite channels, the research sample.

Sixth: A community appointed by him

The research community represents the Iraqi satellite channels that covered the October demonstrations, and this channel was chosen according to criteria that the researcher deems appropriate to conduct his study, where Al-Iraqiya channel represents the general line of the state and is a semi-official channel, while Al-Itijah channel represents one of the channels of the Union of Islamic Radios and Channels, and the Dijla channel represents a partisan channel opposed to the government, and these three channels differ in their orientations and general policies. Through this community, the researcher seeks to know the frameworks of political analysis in his newsletters. The research sample consisted of analyzing news releases for the period (October 1, 2019) until (December 31, 2020) in a comprehensive inventory of all interviews with political analysts mentioned in the newsletters.

Validity: The researcher relied on hypothetical honesty, and presented a content analysis model to a group of experts specialized in media and psychology ([1] □) to express their opinions about the contents of the questionnaire from the main and sub-categories, and to know the extent of the interdependence, clarity and ability of the categories to reach the results that the research aims to her. The reliability of the analysis: In his research, the method used to re-test, where he subjected the same content again to the analysis by another, and when applying the Holst equation, he found that the percentage of agreement between the two analyzes was a researcher (96%), which is a high percentage after analyzing a proportion of the sample amounted to (10%).

Define concepts and terms

- Political analysis frameworks :It is the sum of the frameworks that were presented in political analysis in the news bulletins of the channels, the sample of the research, and related to the issue of demonstrations, according to which political analysts classified the events, whether they were the frameworks of reasons, holding responsibility, or frameworks for proposed solutions to address the issue and other frameworks.
- Iraqi satellite channels :We mean the Iraqi satellite channels that covered the events of the demonstrations in their news bulletins on a daily basis, from which the researcher chose three channels for study.
- Demonstrations :They are demanding demonstrations that started on the first of October 2019 in Baghdad and the central and southern governorates, accompanied by various events that resulted in hundreds of martyrs and wounded, followed by other positions, including internal and external, which eventually led to the realization of a set of demands.

Previous studies

(Muthanna Faihan) (Fayhan, 2017)

The problem of this study is in the attention given by Arab satellite events to the Yemeni crisis, and the nature of news coverage related to local, regional and international political agendas, their objectives and directions for drafting and framing, and their determinants and trends in particular. (What are the trends of news coverage in Arab satellite channels about the Yemeni crisis and the implications of this coverage on trends? • From the Iraqi public) the sample channels represented Al-Mayadeen and Al-Arabiya Al-Hadath, and this research is descriptive in my eyes. The researcher applied both the analytical and field survey methodologies, and the researcher analyzed for a period of three months a sample of the evening news broadcasts on the two channels.

(Adnan Lafta) (Mannan, 2019)

The study aimed to identify the role of frameworks of criticism and mathematical analysis in the Iraqi press, to reveal the frameworks used in the issues that were focused on, and to compare points of agreement and disagreement between the newspapers that were attacked. . Study and use of criticism and analysis and their role in promoting public attitudes towards sports issues. The problem of the study was formulated through the following main question (What is the role of the frameworks of criticism and sports analysis in influencing the public? Attitudes towards sports issues), and this study is one of the descriptive studies in which the researcher relied on the survey method. In both parts of the content analysis of a sample of newspapers represented by morning, time, stadiums, sports and youth, were analyzed. A sample of these newspapers or the other part of the study is the sample questionnaire that the researcher provided to an intended sample of a sports community in the city.

(Jihan) (Yahya, 2013)

This study focused on analyzing the forms of foreign television channels' dealing with the most important issues in the Middle East, and sought to identify the most prominent issues addressed by these sites, to reveal the frameworks in which these issues and the problem were raised. In this study, frameworks for dealing with Middle Eastern issues were identified in CNN, Russia Today and BBC websites, and the trends of these media on the mentioned issues were analyzed, and compared with the policy of the countries with which they work. Belongs to. The study is one of the descriptive studies that relied on the survey method based on the theory of news frames using a guaranteed analytical model.

Theoretical framework

The concept of political analysis

Political analysis is defined as (a deep awareness of the roots of politics and its results through the elements of strategic thought and its alignment with the nature of events, their trajectories, the form of motives, their elements and their apparent active tools, which leads to the person responsible for making internal events and crises that seek to bring about change from them, and a comprehensive understanding of historical evidence Similarities in the context of political events and awareness of the motives related to them, prediction of developments and their results, and making recommendations related to the event that are related to conclusions, hypotheses and applicable) (Al-Azzawi, 2018, pg. 59), as defined as: (a research process in the possible course of interactions Political forces in society and a clear scientific explanation of the type of relationship between internal political forces, and the choices that can be linked to them. Political phenomena and events locally, regionally and globally, and therefore needs to understand the political reality of the country, which needs effective political thinking, to understand the reality of politics which is a complex matter very) (Ibrahim, 2015,

p. 13), and political analysis (a arithmetic process to know the reality, after dismantling describe the conflict axes in the case, after identifying the influential issues and the reasons) (Religion, 2014, p. 14) Political events carry more than one indicator, and this is what necessitates the political analyst to follow the parts of the phenomenon, identify its branches, return them to the simplest and most accurate elements, and scrutinize the conflicting information in them, through what he sees. He possesses insight, accumulated experience, and advanced intellectual skill in studying the transformations of political reality without violating frameworks. Reality of events and this can only be done if those responsible for the analysis attach importance to “political thought and political theory”. Because it is one of the important matters that must be relied upon in forming a mental conception to explain the phenomena, as political thought is concerned with ideas and concepts that search for political phenomena and try to identify them in order, description, study and analysis. To form a specific vision that helps in interpretation based on the ideas formulated by the human mind (Al Kareem, 2020).

Framing concept

The American sociologist is the first to use the term framework in the social science literature Batson (in 1955, where he worked to develop the concept of frameworks, and later researchers' studies continued to consolidate this concept in social studies until contributions came. (Kauffman) 1974, describing the term Frames as a tool used to classify and organize information and experiences, and wrote a book entitled (Frame Analysis), which is considered the founder of the framing approach at that time, and then came the first practical application of frame analysis in media studies after the efforts of the researcher (Tochman) in two studies conducted in 1976 and 1978 , they employed framework analysis as a methodological tool for analyzing the content of the news, then (Intman) worked on rooting the concept of framework analysis theory in media studies, and conducting many studies in this regard (Al-Dubaisi, 2017, p. 83), the idea of forming media frameworks Psychology, who sees that modifications in the definitions of rulings lead to a change in them, and sociology links frameworks in the media to existing social values and beliefs (Abdul Hamid, 2004, p. 403)

Hence and in media studies one news and theoretical frameworks for modern tributaries, providing a systematic explanation of the role of the media in shaping audience attitudes about unresolved issues, and the relationship of those responses to public knowledge. and sympathy with those issues, as the theory of news frames posits “that transcription does not involve in itself, but rather has a certain meaning, but rather acquires its importance by placing it in a framework (framework) that defines, organizes and gives it. It is a degree of consistency, by focusing on some aspect of the subject others are ignored, and media framing is that central idea around which the events of a particular issue are organized (Mr., 2008, p. 348) Goffman. Framing from a social perspective is the method that allows its users to identify, portray, diagnose and categorize everyday incidents (Goffman.E., 1974). , p.21), and knowing (Entman Framing is the selection of some aspect of reality and making i more prominent in the communicative message in order to promote a specific definition, causal explanation, moral evaluation, or recommendation to address a problem. (Entman, 1993, p. 52), the framework It is the central idea around which the news content is organized and that would provide the appropriate context to determine the nature of the issue through the use of selection and confirmation methods (Al-Dabisi, 2017, p. mass communication It is governed by a specific cultural context, through the selection of the person responsible for the communication process for some. Aspects of reality, and focusing on them by highlighting them in their various texts using other mechanisms and tools and in light of professional and ideological standards and variables to achieve the desired response from the public through the conceptual tools that individuals and the media rely on. In conveying, interpreting, and evaluating information (Gorp, 2007, p. 62) it serves to make some ideas more prominent in the news text, others less prominent and other identifiers. Completely invisible. (Entman.RM., 1991, p. 7), and through the foregoing, it can be said that the media, especially television, frame events in such a way that the content fits with what is intended to be presented to the audience through framing mechanisms of “appearance, selection, deletion and exclusion”

The scientific framework

Sub-categories of the main frameworks contained in political analysis in the newscasts of the channels, the sample of the research

Table No. (1) Shows the sub-categories of the solutions frameworks proposed by political analysts to the issue of the demonstrations

%	Total	direction		Tigris		Iraqi		for channel Category	No
	T	%	T	%	T	%	T		
12.3	80	8.8	18	12	27	15.9	35	Creating job opportunities and recruiting graduates	1
12.1	79	16.6	34	9.3	21	10.9	24	Adoption of a new election law and the formation of an independent commission	2
11	72	12.2	25	8.9	20	12.3	27	Unite the demands of the protesters	3
10.3	67	12.2	25	4	9	15th	33	Forming government committees	4

								to implement the demands of the demonstrators	
10.3	67	8.3	17	10.7	24	11.8	26	Combating corruption within state institutions	5
9.1	59	8.3	17	10.7	24	8.3	18	hold early elections	6
8.8	57	6.3	13	16.7	38	2.7	6	Expedite the detection of the killers of the demonstrators	7
8.5	55	9.8	20	5.3	12	10.4	23	Adoption of the commandments of the supreme religious authority	8
6.7	43	10.2	21	3.6	8	6.4	14	The cooperation of the three authorities	9
5.8	38	2.9	6	11.6	26	2.7	6	Changing the government of Adel Abdul Mahdi	10
5.1	33	4.4	9	7.2	16	3.6	8	Formation of a government of competencies	11
100	650	100	205	100	225	100	220	Total	

Table No. (1) Shows the categories of solutions frameworks that were mentioned in the political analysis of the issue of the demonstrations in the three channels. The category of "job creation and employment for graduates" came within the first categories with a rate of (12.3%), while the category of "approval" came in second place. A new election law and the formation of a new commission with a percentage of (12.1%), third place in the categories of "unifying the demands of the demonstrators" with (11%), and fourth place in the category of demonstrators. "Formation of government committees to implement the demands of the demonstrators" with a percentage of (10.3), and in the fourth place came the category of "fighting corruption within state institutions" (10.3), and it came in fifth in the category. • Holding early elections with a percentage of (9.1) to come in sixth place in the category of "Speeding up the detection of the killers of demonstrators." The percentage reached (8.8%), while it ranked seventh in the categories of "approving the wills with the rank of the highest religious authority", and the percentage reached (8.5%), and it ranked eighth in the category of "cooperation". The three authorities." The percentage was estimated at (6.7%) and it ranked ninth in the category of "Changing Adel Abdul-Mahdi's government" with (5.8%) to come in the tenth and last place in the "formation" category, and "the government of competencies" (5.1%)

We note from the above table that the three channels tried to provide solutions to the issue of the demonstrations and then a crisis occurred, and solutions must be developed through what the analyst suggested, but the politicians' vision of solutions differs from one channel. To another and this difference is due to the congruence of the opinions of political analysts with the channels that host them.

Table No. (2) Shows the warning frames that were mentioned in the political analysis in the news releases of the channels of the research sample.

%	Total	Direction		Tigris		Iraqi		the channel Category	No
	T	%	T	%	T	%	T		
14.7	63	7.8	11	25.6	45	6.2	7	Use of excessive violence to suppress demonstrations	1
13.9	60	20.6	29	10.8	19	10.7	12	Exploiting demonstrations from outside parties	2
12.1	52	15.6	22	2.3	4	23.2	26	Departing from the peaceful demonstration	3
12.1	52	12.7	18	5.1	9	22.3	25	Fears of criminals infiltrating the squares	4
11.9	51	6.4	9	14.3	25	15.2	17	Nomination of non-independent personalities for prime minister	5
11.8	50	13.5	19	13.6	24	6.2	7	The political class is betting on the time factor in the end of the demonstrations	6
6.9	30	5	7	11.3	20	2.7	3	Attitudes of international organizations on the use of violence	7
6.8	29	13.5	19	00	00	9	10	Negative consequences of the government's resignation	8
4.9	21	3.5	5	8	14	1.8	2	targeting diplomatic missions	9
4.9	21	1.4	2	9	16	2.7	3	Back to Chapter Seven	10

100	429	100	141	100	176	100	112	Total
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Table No. (2) Of the warning frames presented by political analysts during their interviews in the news bulletins shows a group of groups they focused on so as not to derail the demonstrations, and in the category of warning frames and "excessive violence to suppress them." Demonstrations "in the first place. The "exploitation of demonstrations from external parties" came in second place with a rate of (13.9%), and the "demonstration from peaceful demonstrations" category came in third place with 14.7%. From (. 12.1%) and in the same degree The third "fears of criminals infiltrating the squares" came with the same percentage (12.1%), while the "independent personalities of the prime minister" category came in the fourth place with 11.9%.%, and the fifth place in the mirror category, New Hampshire. The time at the end of the demonstrations with a rate of (11.7%), and in the category of "attitudes of international organizations towards the use of the eighth rank" was "targeting diplomatic missions" (e) with a rate of (4.9%), and with the same percentage, the category of "returning to the seventh chapter" (4.9%) Rank last among the categories. The fact that this framework obtained this percentage indicates the sensitivity of political analysts in the channels of the research sample to the danger posed by the events of the demonstrations on the reality in the country, which prompted them to issue warnings of the situation slipping into the country Country. Unknown, and the inevitable necessities of treatment before it is too late, especially with regard to the consequences of "excessive violence" and fear of foreign intervention, and the fall of Iraq again under the weight of international sanctions as a result of events, and a warning The tires varied between the channels, each according to its direction and focus on which side.

Table No. (3) Shows the frameworks for the causes of the demonstrations issue, which appeared in the political analysis in the news bulletins of the channels of the research sample.

%	Total	Direction		Tigris		Iraqi		the channel Category	No
	T	%	T	%	T	%	T		
17.9	76	15.8	25	16.2	23	22.4	28	Citizens lose confidence in the political process	1
17.4	74	19	30	18.3	26	14.4	18	Mismanagement of the demonstration file	2
14.8	63	11.4	18	14.8	21	19.2	24	lack of social justice	3
11.7	50	12	19	11.3	16	12	15th	Rotating specific personalities in government positions	4
10.2	43	7.6	12	14.7	21	8	10	Parties control the joints of the state	5
9	38	7.6	12	5	7	15.2	19	Ignoring the solutions and recommendations of the religious reference	6
6.6	28	9.5	15th	3.5	5	6.4	8	Constitution restriction of government	7
5.4	23	00	00	16.2	23	00	00	The loyalty of some political forces to Iran	8
4.7	20	10.8	17	00	00	2.4	3	Adel Abdul Mahdi's exit from the American circle	9
2.3	10	6.3	10	00	00	00	00	Non-normalization with Israel	10
100	425	100	158	100	142	100	125	Total	

We note from Table No. (3) The reasons that accumulated and eventually led to the outbreak of the demonstrations. The category "Loss of Citizen's Confidence in the Political Process" came first and scored (17.9%), while it came in second place at the level of groups, and the category (mismanagement of the demonstrations file) won with 17.4 %.) The "social injustice" category came in third place with a percentage of 14.8%, and in the third place came the "rotation of some personalities in government positions" and its percentage. (11.7%) The "party control over the state's joints" category ranked fifth with (10.2%), while the category "ignoring the solutions and recommendations of the religious reference" ranked sixth among the categories and seventh in "constitutional restriction". In the category of government "with a percentage of (6.6%), and the category of loyalty of some political forces to Iran ranked eighth. The percentage (4.7%) was ninth, as was the category of "Adel Abdul-Mahdi's exit from the American circle" (4.7%), and it ranked tenth And the last one is in the category of "normalization of blood with Israel" and the ratio reached (2.3%)The interest in this framework comes from analyzing and crystallizing the causes and accumulations of the subject of the demonstrations, and from the political analysts who appeared in the research channels, and focused on the causes of the events of the demonstrations, and sought to list, classify and clarify them. Categorized under internal and external frameworks. The "vibration" between the people and the authority on the one hand, and the urgent external factors on the other hand, according to what was presented in the analysis, which differ from one

channel to another according to its policy and method of adoption. The event and the reasons it wants to issue led to the deterioration of the situation.

Table No. (4) Shows the conflict frameworks that were diagnosed in the political analysis of the issue of demonstrations in the channels of the research sample.

%	Total	Direction		Tigris		Iraqi		the channel Category	No
	T	%	T	%	T	%	T		
19.4	76	25	40	14.9	25	17.6	11	Intersection of interests between parties	1
19.2	75	15.6	25	13.1	22	44.4	28	Controversies over choosing a new prime minister	2
15.6	61	11.3	18	21.4	36	11.1	7	The conflict between the protesters and the government	3
9	35	5.6	9	11.3	19	11.1	7	Targeting the "third party" of the demonstrators	4
8.7	34	00	00	20.2	34	00	00	Militia control of the government	5
8.7	34	2.5	4	17.9	30	00	00	Iran-US conflict	6
5.6	22	10.6	17	00	00	7.9	5	Exploitation of demonstrations by Kurdish and Sunni parties	7
5.1	20	12.5	20	00	00	00	00	Insulting the crowd	8
4.6	18	11.3	18	00	00	00	00	The US-Israeli targeting of the resistance axis	9
4.1	16	5.6	9	1.2	2	7.9	5	Burning party headquarters	10
100	391	100	160	100	168	100	63	Total	

The results of the above table regarding conflict frameworks were as follows: The "intersection of interests of the parties" ranked first with a percentage of the total three channels (19.4%), followed by "disputes choosing a new prime minister." It ranked second with a percentage of (19.2). As for the "conflict between protesters and the government" category, it ranked third with a percentage of (15.6%), and it came in fourth place in the category of "third parties targeting protesters" with (9%), followed by it. From the fifth category "militia control". The government" and this group's percentage (8.7%), and is equal to the "Iran-American conflict" category and the same percentage (8.7%), and it replaced the "exploitation of Kurdish and Sunni demonstrations" category in sixth place. Parties" and the percentage was estimated at (5.6%), while it ranked seventh in the "insulting the public" category with (5.1%), then the "American-Israeli targeting of the resistance axis" category came in eighth place (4.6%), and ninth and last in the category (burning party headquarters) and the rate was (4.1%) In the political analysis of the issue of the demonstrations, we note the focus of the political analysts on the "conflict" side as the main cause of the issue, and they put in their analyzes classifications of the conflict distributed between the internal conflict between the two parties. The political parties themselves, and between the regime and the people who blew up the crisis in this way, not to mention the conflict of the international community on Iraqi soil, which wanted to exploit the crisis to achieve its goals in one way or another. And each channel deals with the conflict in accordance with its orientations.

Table No. (5) Shows the frameworks of humanitarian concerns that were mentioned in the political analysis of the demonstrations issue in the news bulletins of the channels of the research sample.

%	Total	direction		Tigris		Iraqi		the channel Category	No
	T	%	T	%	T	%	T		
42.8	115	42.9	36	41.5	46	44.6	33	Condemning the fall of martyrs and wounded among the demonstrators	1
13.7	37	8.3	7	23.4	26	5.4	4	Condemnation of attacks on journalists and activists	2
13.7	37	21.4	18	2.7	3	21.6	16	Refusal to involve children in demonstrations	3
11.5	31	19	16	4.5	5	13.5	10	Condemnation of the Al Wathba Square incident	4
10.1	27	4.8	4	16.2	18	6.8	5	Iraq's breach of its obligations in the human rights file	5
8.2	22	3.6	3	11.7	13	8.1	6	The support of the United Nations representative in Baghdad to the demonstrators	6
100	269	100	84	100	111	100	74	Total	

The results of Table No. (5) Related to the humanitarian frameworks included in the political analysis show the order of the following categories: The category "Condemnation of the Fall of Martyrs and Wounded Demonstrators" ranked first and foremost. 42.8% is followed by second place. Focusing on assaulting and clearing demonstrations, with a rate of 13.7%. In the same place came the category of "refusal to involve children in demonstrations" with a rate equal to the previous one (13.7%), while the third category "condemnation of the Al-Wathba Square incident" came with a rate of (11.5%).). The category "Iraq's violation of its obligations in the human rights file" came in the fourth place with a percentage of (10.1%), and in the fifth and last place came the category "the support of the United Nations representative in Baghdad to the demonstrators" with (8.2%). The political aspect in the channels of the research sample is the humanitarian aspect. Accompanying the demonstrations in terms of acts of violence represented by killings, victims and wounded, demonstrators who violate international human rights regulations, and calls by international organizations to stop the accompanying violations, and this is what the channels tried to shed light on through interviews with political analysts

Table No. (6) Shows the legal frameworks mentioned in the political analysis of the issue of demonstrations in the channels of the research sample.

%	Total		direction		Tigris		Iraqi		the channel Category	No
	T		%	T	%	T	%	T		
37.3	87		26.5	22	50.7	35	37	30	Activating the role of the judiciary	1
21.9	51		24.1	20	4.4	3	34.6	28	It is illegal to close government departments and institutions	2
17.2	40		16.7	14	23.2	16	12.4	10	Solve the problem of the largest mass according to the law	3
17.2	40		20.5	17	21.7	15 th	9.9	8	Enact new laws to deal with the current situation	4
6.4	15 th		12.2	10	00	00	6.1	5	Accountability of inciting media according to legal frameworks	5
100	233		100	83	100	69	100	81	Total	

The results of the legal frameworks included in the political analysis showed the following: Among the categories, the "activating the role of the judiciary" category ranked first with a rate of (37.3%), then ranked second in the "judicial authority" category. - The illegality of closing government departments and institutions, with a percentage of (21.9%), while the category of "solving the problem of the largest bloc according to the law" ranked third with a rate of 17.2%. The category of "enacting new laws to deal with the current situation" came in the equivalent in the ranking (17.2%) and the "media incitement to accountability according to the law" category came in fourth place with a percentage of (6.4%). The legal description that emerged from the political analysis of the demonstrations issue was manifested in several axes, legally and administratively, and resorting to the law without favoritism or bias, namely Frameworks represented in finding comprehensive and unified solutions to the crisis of demonstrations away from any temporary or fragmented solutions, and the stronger the role of the judiciary, the greater the application of the law for all without inclination to a particular party and this is what the political analysis focused on in the channels of the research sample.

Table No. (7) Shows the keywords that were mentioned in the political analysis in the news releases of the research sample channels.

%	Total		direction		Tigris		Iraqi		the channel Category	No
	T		%	T	%	T	%	T		
29.2	92		34	33	19.4	30	46	29	snipers	1
22.2	70		15.5	15 th	27.1	42	20.6	13	third party	2
15.9	50		5.2	5	25.8	40	7.7	5	Revolution	3
15.9	50		28.8	28	5.2	8	22.1	14	infiltrated	4
11.1	35		00	00	22.5	35	00	00	militias	5
5.7	18		16.5	16	00	00	3.6	2	joker gangs	6
100	315		100	97	100	155	100	63	Total	

Table (7) shows the keywords mentioned in the political analysis, where "snipers" ranked first with a percentage (29.2%), followed by the "third party" label with a percentage of (22.2%), then. It ranked third with a rate of (22.2%). revolution" with a percentage of (15.9%), and the name "Mendson" is equivalent to it, and with the same percentage (15.9%). The "militias" ranked fourth with (11.1%), and "Joker gangs" came in fifth and last place with (5.7%), and the words the main presented in political analysis Diversity in the research sample channels, what is common in one channel and what is not necessarily found in another, which is the product of analysts' opinions and description of the topic, and most often it is consistent with the policy of that channel.

Table No. (8) Shows the active forces that were mentioned in the political analysis of the demonstrations issue in the channels of the research sample.

%	Total		direction		Tigris		Iraqi		the channel Category	No
	T		%	T	%	T	%	T		
33.7	93		38	32	19.8	21	46.5	40	Religious reference in Najaf	1
21.5	59		36.9	31	12.3	13	17.4	15th	United State	2
18.2	50		16.7	14	16	17	22.1	19	political leaders	3
14.6	41		8.4	7	24.5	26	9.3	8	Human rights organizations	4
12	33		00	00	27.4	29	4.7	4	Iran	5
100	276		100	84	100	106	100	86	Total	

The results of Table No. (8) Revealed the active forces that had an active role in the subject of the demonstrations and on which political analysts focused during the political analysis in the news bulletins in the channels of the research sample, so it ranked first. . As an active force in the "religious reference in Najaf" category, it got 33.7%, followed by the "United States" category, which ranked second as an active force in the subject, with a rate of (21.5%). And came in third place the category of "political leaders". With 18.2%, it ranked third. The fourth category is "human rights organizations" with 14.6% and in the fifth and last place came "Iran" with 12%, and the roles of the active force in the demonstrations vary, according to a political analysis. Analysts, between what is positive wants to end the crisis and mitigate its severity, and what is negative increases tension, and this difference is due to accusations leveled at some parties and states of interfering in the internal affairs of Iraq. Analysts took it during political analysis.

The most important results

1. The proposed solutions framework ranked first among the frameworks in which political analysts rated the issue, and Al-Iraqiya channel topped the category of "job creation and employment of graduates" and the formation of government committees to implement the demonstrators' demands. Dijla channel focused on "accelerating the detection of the killers of the demonstrators." And the change of Adel Abdul-Mahdi's government, "The solutions proposed by analysts at Dijla TV come because the opposition channel is a political government, and Al-Tayar channel focused on "unifying the demands of the demonstrators" and forming government committees to implement the demands. Mahdi.
2. Political analysts at Al-Iraqiya channel tried to warn against "a departure from peaceful demonstrations and fears of infiltration into the arenas of criminal demonstrations," while the political analysis in the warning frameworks on Dijla channel focused on the category of "excessive violence." Nomination of non-independent personalities for prime minister. As for Al-Etjiah TV, its warning frameworks focused on "staying away from peaceful demonstrations and the political class's bet on the factor of time to end the demonstrations."
3. Reasons frameworks ranked third within the frameworks that political analysts focused on, and came on Al-Iraqiya channel in the category "Loss of Citizen's Trust in the Political Process and Absence of Social Justice" in the first place. As for the political analysis of Dijla channel, it emphasized "the mismanagement of the demonstrations file and the loyalty of some forces." Political analysts on Al-Etjiah channel converged with Al-Iraqiya in the category of "losing the citizen's confidence in the political process" and with Dijla TV in the category of "mismanagement of the demonstrations file."
4. Political analysts on the three channels paid attention to the current conflict, and focused on Al-Iraqiya channel on "the differences in choosing the prime minister," while the political analysis on Dijla channel focused on the "Iran-American conflict." Party control of the government. As for Al-Itjiah TV, its political analysts focused on "insulting the popular crowd."
5. The views of the political analysts converged in the frameworks of the humanitarian aspects, and the results of the groups were similar and were represented in "condemning the martyrs and wounded protesters" and refusing to involve children in the demonstrations, ie: the humanitarian aspects agreed upon by political analysts in all cases, even if they differ in other frameworks for reasons related Analysts or political trends followed in the channels of the research sample.
6. In the political analysis of Al-Iraqiya channel, the labels "snipers and infiltrators" came at the forefront of the words, and on the Dijla channel, political analysts focused on the "third party and the revolution", while the newspaper "Etjiah" said. Converged with the Iraqi channel in its nomenclature.
7. The political analysis in the three channels focused on some of the active forces that had a prominent role in the demonstrations, whether that was a positive or negative role. The political analysis of Al-Iraqiya channel gave importance to the "religious reference and political leaders", while the political analysis on Dijla channel emphasized the "human rights organizations". The actor responded as a supportive force to the participants, and political analysts at Dijla TV focused on the negative role of Iran. As for the channel, the political analysis emphasized the role of the "religious reference" as an effective force that

provides solutions. As for the role of the United States, it is a negative one, according to the viewpoint of political analysts in Al-Ittijah Channel.

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